

Communication, Dissemination and Demonstration Report

WP5: Communication, Dissemination and Demonstration

D 5.2: Communication, Dissemination and Demonstration Report

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Table of content

Document Information	1
Document history	2
Abbreviations	3
Participants	4
Document summary	5
Document content	5
<i>Part. 1 Summary of the Communication and Dissemination Activities</i>	<i>5</i>
1.1 Introduction.....	5
1.2 Summary of actions during the first year	6
<i>Part. 2 KPI-status after 12 months</i>	<i>7</i>
2.1 Dissemination portfolio.....	7
2.2 KPIs for project activities after 12 months compared with targets	7
2.3 Additional comments regarding specific dissemination activities.....	10
2.3.1. Website.....	10
2.3.2. Social media: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn	10
2.3.3.E-newsletter	10
2.3.4 Videos.....	11
<i>Part. 3 Summary</i>	<i>11</i>
3.1. Obstacles	11
3.1. Positive examples.....	11

Document Information

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TABLE 1: DOCUMENT INFORMATION

¹ PU = public | PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services) | RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services) | CO= Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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TABLE 2: DOCUMENT HISTORY

Abbreviations

EC	EUROPEAN COMMISSION	WP	WORK PACKAGE
GA	GRANT AGREEMENT	GAS	INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS
EU	EUROPEAN UNION	OG	OPERATIONAL GROUP
EIP	EUROPEAN INNOVATION PARTNERSHIP	AKIS	AGRICULTURAL KNOWLEDGE INFORMATION SYSTEM
CDS	COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY	CAP	COMMON AGRICULTURAL POLICY
KPI	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR		

TABLE 3: ABBREVIATIONS

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TABLE 4: PARTICIPANTS

Document summary

This document contains a summary of the communication and dissemination activities that have been performed in the first 12 months of the Oper8 project: European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control. It has received grants under the topic Horizon-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-23, grant agreement No 101060591, – Broaden EIP Operational Group outcomes by means of thematic networks, compiling and sharing knowledge ready for practice.

The document comprises three main sections:

1. **General Summary of Communication Activities (Section 1):** This section provides a broad overview of the communication activities carried out during the project's inaugural year. It highlights the key initiatives, strategies, and milestones achieved in terms of disseminating project-related information and engaging stakeholders.
2. **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for WP5 (Section 2):** In this section, a table is presented listing the KPIs identified as pertinent to Work Package 5 (WP5). Each KPI is accompanied by detailed comments elucidating their relevance and significance within the context of the project. This section offers a comprehensive assessment of the project's performance against specific performance metrics.
3. **Summary of Experiences from the First Year (Section 3):** The final section offers a concise summary of the insights and experiences gained during the project's initial year. It provides a reflective perspective on the challenges faced, lessons learned, and notable achievements made within the project's early stages.

Collectively, this document aims to provide a comprehensive account of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken in the Oper 8 project's first year, offering valuable insights into its progress and contributions to the broader objectives of the thematic network.

Part. 1 Summary of the Communication and Dissemination Activities.

1.1 Introduction

During the first year of the project, communication routines were established, and communication materials were produced to facilitate the dissemination of project knowledge across all the project's markets.

Strategies for reaching various target groups were deliberated upon and the protocols for meetings in WP5 were set and further developed. A total of thirteen (13) meetings were convened, with the latest meeting being conducted within the T 5.2. group, while the rest of the meetings generally focused on discussing WP5 issues. Moving forward, it is intended that T 5.2. meetings will be scheduled at approximately monthly intervals initially, with a reduced frequency of about every other month thereafter. Similarly, WP5 meetings will be held with an interval of approximately one (1) meeting every other month. The posting of materials on social media will now be escalated by the T. 5.2. group. A tutorial for uploading posts have recently been made available for the project participants. Previously, this responsibility had primarily been undertaken by Agroväst, but in order to reach the project's goals, this activity will be performed by all partners to reach all markets in which the project is active.

1.2 Summary of actions during the first year

In principle the actions indicated in the plan for the first year has been followed according to Table 5. The website was in place by the end of 2022 and concurrently, social media channels were activated. The website now encompasses comprehensive information about all project partners complete with links to their respective organisations and the Operational Groups (OGs). Additionally, it provides details about past and upcoming events. Importantly, the web site is available in all partner languages, ensuring broad accessibility.

All foundational communication materials, as specified in the Visual Identity Handbook, were promptly developed at the project's outset and subsequently featured prominently in numerous events, as elaborated in part 2 of the document. During these initial months of the project, press-releases were strategically disseminated to increase project visibility. The project was also highlighted in select publications, thereby expanding its reach to a wider audience. One example is an article in the Swedish magazine Agriculture Business, reporting from the first EU-webinar in April 2023, Solutions for Alternative Weed control #1. Electrical Weeding. In April 2023, an introductory communication video, outlining the objectives and general activities of Oper8, was successfully launched. Newsletters have been produced roughly in accordance with the Communication & Dissemination plan, ensuring a consistent flow of project updates.

Demonstrations have been organised according to the plan, with two demos held in each partner country during the first year. Furthermore, videos related to OGs and demonstration activities have been initiated.

It is worth noting that all the dissemination and communication activities have been registered through a monitoring and reporting process. Partners regularly reported their respective dissemination and communication activities, utilising a shared spreadsheet for data collection. This spreadsheet includes details such as the partners name, the type of dissemination/communication action, the channel or media used, as well as the date, the type and number of audiences reached, and evidence of the activity (e.g., pictures, links, news pieces, etc.). In the communication spreadsheet, one sheet is dedicated to demonstration activities, while another covers various communication activities.

In Table 5, the core activities during the projects' first year are pinpointed as well as the activities that are primarily meant to be dealt with later. To some extent, activities in this category have started already (see part 2).

1st year	2nd-3rd year		After the project
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning launching Communication Actions • Preparation of basic communication materials • Website and social media in place 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of communication strategies • Social networks • Stakeholder workshops, conferences and webinars • Demonstrations • Podcasts, e-learning tools. videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of communication strategies • Social networks • Scientific publications • Press releases • Stakeholder workshops • Demonstrations • Podcasts, e-learning tools, videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social networks • Scientific publications • Press releases • Stakeholder workshops

TABLE 5: CORE ACTIVITIES DURING THE PROJECT'S LIFETIME

Part. 2 KPI-status after 12 months.

2.1 Dissemination portfolio

All dissemination messages as well as the overall design will be tailored to take into consideration the target audience and context of the institution or country in question and will be integrated into different tools. These messages will be seamlessly integrated into various communication tools. It is worth noting that some of the tools outlined in the Communication & Dissemination Plan have undergone updates. These tools include:

- Oper8 website
- Social media
- Development of Promotional materials
- Press releases
- Newsletters
- Workshops
- Scientific publications
- Seminars
- Videos
- Podcasts
- Fact sheets, practice abstracts
- Training material including e-learning modules
- Final Conference

The way in which Oper8 will be perceived from the targeted audience will be a consequence of the outcomes and the communication of these outcomes. Therefore, a consistent and positive image has to be created by using corporate brand identity. The image created here will build trust and responsiveness from the project partners, and other key stakeholders.

Building a corporate identity seeks to streamline the utilization of specific graphic and visual parameters across all participants by following predefined guidelines and templates. The choice of communication channel depends on the desired impact. At times, simply providing information through a one-way process of conveying facts or explanations may suffice. In such cases, platforms like an intranet article, external web content, or email communication may be the most appropriate channels. On the other hand, when the goal is to foster comprehension, commitment, and impact, two-way communication is indispensable. This often necessitates repeated meetings and dialogues to ensure effective engagement and understanding among stakeholders.

2.2 KPIs for project activities after 12 months compared with targets

In Table 6, the KPIs from the Communication and Dissemination Plan are listed together with some additional KPIs in the impact section of the project of which we consider are relevant to report here. Short comments are also given.

Dissemination Action	Target	After 12 months	Comment
Social media presence (LinkedIn, Facebook Twitter)	Number of posts in social media during project lifetime: 360	92	Somewhat below target, but it took some time to accumulate relevant materials in the beginning of the project. Twitter (X) posts in UK dominate so far.

Social media presence (LinkedIn, Facebook Twitter)	Number of followers during the project's lifetime: 2000	297	Below target, same reason as above, LinkedIn followers dominate.
Conferences and webinars	Number of consumer/technical conferences and webinars: 70	35	High activity in all markets and high diversity of events.
Project Website	Total number of visits: visits to the portal: 20000	1100	Below target. Reasons could be that the website was not up directly as the project started, and it has also taken some time to add interesting materials.
Publications	Number of papers published during project lifetime: 60	6	More or less according to plan. Intention primarily to report when Best practices, National Action Plans etc. have been set and will be communicated.
Project Leaflets, Brochures, posters, banners, roll-ups	Number of distributed printed/digital materials: 20000	About 1000	Below target. Although materials have not been handed out to a large extent, posters, banners and roll-ups have been displayed for large audiences. Dissemination materials have also been provided with QR-codes to large extents, providing opportunities to get access to digital information.
Demonstrations	Number of demonstrations: 56	22	Above target: High activity in all markets. Diverse topics and diverse participants.
National and European Workshops	Number of Attendants: 280	0	Will be performed within WP3 that commences in October 2023.
E-newsletters	Number of newsletters produced: 11 (Four each year 2023 and 2024 and 3 2025).	3	At target.
E-newsletter	Number of subscribers: 3500	249	Below target. Newsletters have recently started to be produced more regularly, with one each month from July onwards. The number of subscribers should increase when the platform gets more established. It has been discussed that they might need to be produced more often to meet the subscriber target.
Press releases	Number of Press releases: 30	10	According to plan: All partners have informed about the project on their web sites.
Introductory communication video	Number of videos: 1	1	Target reached

Audio-visual materials, videos	Number of videos presenting Best Practice solutions etc: 50	3	These will primarily be produced within T4.2, which has not yet started. The videos produced is in one case based on a demo-event and in two cases based on OGs. Instruction for production of videos has been set. Several videos from Demo-events are right now being produced.
Podcasts	Number of podcasts: 24	0	Will be produced within T4.2 that has not started yet.
Practice abstracts	Number of Practice abstracts produced: 100	2	These will primarily be produced within T4.2, which has not yet started. The Practice abstracts produced are summarizing two OGs.
Fact sheets	Number of Fact sheets produced: 80	0	Will primarily be produced within T 4.2, that has not started yet.
Summary of Practice abstracts, fact sheets and audio-visual materials	Number of views: 10000	0	Will primarily be produced within T4.2 that has not started yet
Links with other EU/National projects	Number of links: 15	3	No formal agreements signed yet, but 3 cooperations have started informally. One shared demo-event occurred in the UK in 2023.
E-learning modules.	Number of enrolled stakeholders: 200	0	Will primarily be produced within T4.2 that has not started yet
Training materials including e-learning modules	Number of users: 2100	0	Will primarily be produced within T4.2 that has not started yet
Stakeholders reached through communication channels	Number of stakeholders reached: 30000	1489	Below target. The figure is the sum of the number of YouTube views, followers on social media and visits on the website.
Oper8 activities	Number of Technicians/advisors reached: 140	5800	Above target. Estimated number of technicians/advisors reached on Demos and Conferences, seminars, webinars and workshops
Oper8 activities	Percentage Farmers reached: 40%	42%	Target reached.
CAP-network disseminating Oper-8 knowledge.	Number of networks: 7	2	and the connection to the Booster initiative.
Popular farmer's dissemination channels distributing Oper8 materials	Number of channels: 35	3	Below target. Could vary between countries how many relevant channels that are available.

Partner projects and other OGs integrating Oper8 knowledge	Number of projects: 14	2	AUA has presented Oper-8 at two KoM meetings.
Final Oper8 event.	Number of events: 1	0	To be held later.

TABLE 6: KPIS REGISTERED AT MONTH 12.

2.3 Additional comments regarding specific dissemination activities

2.3.1. Website

The structure of the website set up (www.oper-8.eu) has roughly followed the outline set up in the C&D plan with information about the partners to the left, then information about the OGs and further to the right information about past and upcoming events (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of the website oper-8.eu.

2.3.2. Social media: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn

Core function is to attract attention locally to upcoming events, spread short communications and to increase the interest in the website and e-newsletters. The activities are supposed to accelerate as the dedicated T5.2. Communication Group has been set up. The social media can be reached through the website and on LinkedIn: Oper-8, Facebook: Oper-8 and Twitter (X): @OPER8_EU. The KPIS registered for the Social Media are divided as follows: Of the 297 followers, the majority are following LinkedIn (179), thereafter Twitter (X, 78) and Facebook (39). Only one follower has so far been registered for YouTube. Most posts have been uploaded on Twitter (X, 55), thereafter LinkedIn (24) and only 13 in Facebook.

2.3.3. E-newsletter

E-newsletters have now started to be produced more regularly than in the spring of 2023 and there is a strong emphasis on using this channel now and to attract more subscribers. Leaflets with a QR-code leading to the subscription page for the newsletters have been presented on numerous events lately. The core function for the newsletters is to briefly comment what is happening in the project and to direct the subscribers to the website.

Three newsletters have so far been published and another one is due in October 2023. The topics for the latest newsletter are that the website is now available in seven languages, short information about past events and news about how to reach more information on new and past events on the website.

2.3.4 Videos

Instruction for the production of videos have been distributed, but only a few videos have so far been produced. Most are meant to be produced within WP4.

Part. 3 Summary

3.1. Obstacles

Generally, the spread of information via Oper8 communication channels started slowly but has built up momentum as demonstration events, presentations and the webinar all began through spring and summer 2023. The reasons communication started slowly are three-fold:

- 1) In the project's initial year, there was a relatively small volume of information collected. Consequently, it is natural that interest in the project's website and social media presence was limited. As more data becomes available through survey results, videos and regular webinars, we anticipate a rise in interest and engagement.
- 2) The frequency of posting materials on social media and the website is expected to increase now that more individuals are being introduced to perform these tasks. In general, there is a strong understanding of how to manage these channels in all project markets. After a brief introduction, we anticipate an acceleration in these activities.
- 3) Work Package 5 (Wp 5) primarily functions as a conduit for disseminating the outputs generated in Work Packages 2-4. These outputs have only recently become accessible, so dissemination activities related to them are just beginning.

3.1. Positive examples

The communication activities such as demos, webinars, seminars etc. has reached large audience already. It might be that now after the pandemic, people are both eager to meet and learn things again and at the same time, the digital platforms have been well functioning, and people are accustomed to collect information and communicate through these channels. As an example, there was a large interest in the first Oper-8 European Webinar that was followed by 122 participants from all the countries taking part in the project.